

TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL

- 01-What is your main focus in software engineering?
- 02-How much time do you have working with software development?
- 03-How much time do you have working with agile?
- 04-In the agile teams I've participated in, I consider that the developers/designers shared the leadership of the team
- 05-Before taking part in the experiment, how many times did you take on the role of PO in your professional career?
- 06-During the experiment, did you take on the role of PO?
- 07-I consider the role of PO as one of the team leaders
- 08-Before taking part in the experiment, how many times did you take on the role of SM in your professional career?
- 09-During the experiment, did you take on the role of SM?
- 10-I consider the SM role as one of the team leaders
- 11-[U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to better understand my team's performance.
- 12-[U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to improve my team's performance.
- 13-[U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to better reflect on my team's sub-items of teamwork (Communication, Coordination, Cohesion, Effort, Mutual Support, Balance of Contribution).
- 14-[U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to improve my team's sub-items of teamwork (Communication, Coordination, Cohesion, Effort, Mutual Support, Balance of Contribution).
- 15-[U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to generate Guiding Questions that added value to my team.
- 16-[U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to improve my sharing of leadership among team members.
- 17-[U] The Role Rotation ceremony was better than the Sprint Retrospective at making the team reflect on their teamwork.
- 18-[E] It was easy to learn and use the Role Rotation ceremony.
- 19-[E] I find it easy to understand the Role Rotation ceremony.
- 20-[E] I find it easy to apply the Role Rotation ceremony.
- 21-[E] Using the Role Rotation ceremony made it easier to do my job.
- 22-[E] Using the Role Rotation ceremony made it easier for team members to share leadership.
- 23-In your opinion, what were the main benefits of the Role Rotation ceremony?
- 24-In your opinion, what were the main challenges of the Role Rotation ceremony?
- 25-Do you have any comments on the Role Rotation ceremony, its use and/or implementation?
- 26-Do you have any suggestions for improving the Role Rotation ceremony?
- 27-Would you like to share any additional material that you generated during the experiment?